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MODERN EXODYNAMIC PROCESSES IN THE TBILISI REGION

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Abstract. The geological structure of the Tbilisi territory is complex and diverse, with unique morphology and geodynamic features. This complexity is primarily a result of the geographical location of its geotectonic structures. Specifically, the opposing movements of the Caucasus and Adjara-Trialeti mountain systems during the Late Alpine orogenesis, and their collision with the solid substrate of the Georgian Belt between them, occurred in the final stage of the neotectonic period against a common background of uplift. Geotectonically, the majority of the territory is situated in the zone of the eastern end of the Adjara-Trialeti folded-block structure. The northern and eastern parts transition into the Kartli molasse zone of the Georgian Belt, while the southern part extends into the Tetrtskaro-Asureti and Marneuli subzones of the Artvin-Bolnisi Belt. These areas are characterized by intense subsidence, the accumulation of marine and thick Upper Neogene and Pleistocene continental sediments, and well-developed overthrusts, folds, and disjunctive dislocations. The city is currently undergoing the design and construction of various communication infrastructures in challenging engineering and geological conditions, leading to large-scale exodynamic processes such as deep and lateral erosion of rivers, mudflows, landslides, and rock avalanches. This has resulted in an extremely complicated geoecological situation, with occurrences of torrential-gravitational and suffocation-sedimentary events, groundwater-induced flooding, flash floods, and mudflows from ravines. Consequently, the normal rhythm of city life is periodically disrupted, the safe movement of transport is compromised, and many buildings are deformed and destroyed.

Keywords: Exodynamics, geotectonics, morphology, erosion, landslides, mudslides, Avalanches

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აბსტრაქტი. თბილისის ტერიტორიის გეოლოგიური აგებულება, მისი მორფოლოგია და გეოდინამიკური თავისებურებანი მეტად რთული და მრავალფეროვანია. ეს განპირობებულია პირველყოვლისა მისი გეოტექტონიკური სტრუქტურების გეოგრაფიული მდებარეობით, კერძოდ კავკასიონისა და აჭარა-თრიალეთის მთათა სისტემების ურთიერთსაპირისპირო მოძრაობებით გვიანალპურ ოროგენეზში და მათი შეჯახებით მათ შორის არსებულ საქართველოს ბელტის მყარ სუბსტრატთან, რომელიც მიმდინარეობდა ნეოტექტონიკური პერიოდის ბოლო ეტაპზე აღმავლობის საერთო ფონზე. გეოტექტონიკურად ტერიტორიის უდიდესი ნაწილი მდებარეობს აჭარა-თრიალეთის ნაოჭა-ბლოკური ნაგებობის აღმოსავლური დაბოლოების ზონაში; ტერიტორიის ჩრდილო და აღმოსავლეთი ნაწილები გადადის საქართველოს ბელტის ქართლის მოლასურ ზონა ში, ხოლო მისი სამხრული ნაწილი - ართვინ-ბოლნისის ბელტის თეთრიწყარო-ასურეთისა და მარნეულის ქვეზონებში, რომელიც ხასიათდება ინტენსიური დაძირვით ზღვიური და მძლავრი ზედანეოგენური და პლეისტოცენური კონტინენტური ნალექების დაგროვებით და კარგად გა მოსახული ზეწრული და სხვა ტიპის ნაოჭებით და დიზუნქტიური დისლოკაციებით. ქალაქის ტერიტორიაზე სხვადასხვა კომუნიკაციების დაპროექტება-მშენებლობა მიმდინარეობს ურთულეს საინჟინრო-გეოლოგიურ პირობებში, რასაც შედეგად მოსდევს ფართომასშტაბიანი ეგზოდინამიკური პროცესების (მდინარეთა სიღრმითი და გვერდითი ეროზია, ღვარცოფული ნაკადების წარმოქმნა, მეწყრები, კლდეზვავები) განვითარება და გეოეკოლოგიური სიტუაციის უკიდურესი გართულება. მათ შორის, აღსანიშნავია მეწყულ-გრავიტაციული და სუფოზიურ-ჯდენადი მოვლენები, მიწისქვეშა წყლებით გამოწვეული შეტბორვები, წყალმოვარდნები-დატბორვები და ხევებიდან გამოტანილი ქვატალახოვანი ღვარცოფული ტიპის ნაკადები. შედეგად, პერიოდულად ირღვევა ქალაქის ნორმალური ცხოვრების რიტმი, ექმნება საშიშროება ტრანსპორტის უსაფრთხო მოძრაობას, ხდება მრავალი ნაგებობის დეფორმაცია-ნგრევა.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: ეგზოდინამიკა, გეოტექტონიკა, მორფოლოგია, ეროზია, მეწყრები, ღვარცოფები, კლდეზვავები

Introduction

The period of urbanization of cities is the longest stage, and as a result, no natural environment experiences as much technogenic impact as the territory of large cities. Despite cities only occupying 1% of the world's land, more than half of the planet's population is concentrated in them. By the beginning of the 21st century, the urban population in many developed countries had reached 70-80% [6]. Since the 1990s, ecological changes in urbanized areas have reached a critical threshold, leading to irreversible negative geoecological complications in the geological environment. Modern large cities are now considered anthropogenic systems, where natural landscapes are almost nonexistent, and the sustainability of the anthropogenic landscape relies heavily on human intervention. However, recent efforts have been made to restore natural ecosystems worldwide and develop an ecosystem recovery strategy. In the last few decades of the 20th century, several international conferences were held under the auspices of the UN (Vancouver 1976, Rio de Janeiro 1992, Istanbul 1996) to develop a

program for sustainable development. This program takes into account local historical and cultural heritage conditions and the organization of protected areas of various ranks. According to the World Health Organization, the norm of green space per capita for large cities should be 50 m². From a health perspective, a city is considered poor when green cover is less than 10% and good when it reaches 40-60% [6].

Research methods

During the field studies, we utilized geomorphological and geological methods. Specifically, the morphological method was used to identify the main forms of the terrain, their contours, and arrangement. The morphometric method helped determine the dimensions of these forms, while the morphostructural method allowed us to understand the relationship between the terrain and geological structures. Additionally, various geological methods were employed, including lithological analysis of the material, clarification of the sequence of sedimentary layers formation, and study of the granulometry and roundness of the material.

In the desk work phase, we analyzed literature and cartographic materials related to the topic. The conclusions presented at the end of the article were based on the findings obtained through the methods mentioned above.

Research Results

Tbilisi and its surroundings are located on the border of two large geomorphological regions - the intermontane lowland of North Georgia (the Inner and Lower Kartli lowlands) and the South Georgian plateau, in particular, its northern end - the Trialeti folded system. The relief of Tbilisi clearly distinguishes the high right bank of the Mtkvari River, with ridges arranged in a maras pattern, and the low left bank, with wide, cyclical river terraces [9].

According to the 1876 census, the population of Tbilisi was 104,000 people, and its area was 804 hectares, where 55% of the territory was occupied by various buildings, and 20% was occupied by gardens. By 1921, the city's population had already doubled (230,000 people), increased to 800,000 residents in the period of 20-25 years, and by the 80s it reached 1.5 million people and the built-up area of the city exceeded 35,000 hectares. Due to the fact that there were almost no optimally usable areas left, the city expanded in areas that were considered unacceptable for construction or extremely difficult according to previously accepted engineering geological norms; Such are the tectonically disturbed and steep slopes of Mamadavidi, Nutsubidze plateau, Ikalto and Nadzaladevi-Makhati, as well as ravines filled with household waste and technogenic soil and buried, closed depressions, saline, swampy and extremely sensitive to physical changes rocks [1]. Exodynamic processes in the territory of Tbilisi, due to its geological and geomorphological structure, were actively taking place in the past, and today they have become even more intense as a result of highly activated human economic activity. The geocological complications of the Tbilisi environs reached a crisis state in the second half of the last century and at the beginning of the XXI century.

A clear example of the study of the engineering-geological condition of Tbilisi is G. Japaridze's work "Engineering Geology of Tbilisi"[8], which identifies the main issues that provide an overview of the engineering condition of the area. From this extensive list, we have selected the following issues as a guide:

1. Natural-anthropogenic factors of relief fragmentation and related deformations.
2. Dependence of slope gravitational processes on the relief and geological structure.
3. Rockfalls, landslides, and movements of steep slopes.

One of the key components of the natural environment is the relief on which human economic activities are conducted. The positive and negative outcomes directly impact the development potential of the country. The more complex the relief, the more challenging it becomes to utilize it for various economic purposes, leading to conditions that promote the development of exogeodynamic processes.

The slope of the relief and the depths of erosional incision of rivers determine the coefficient of horizontal fragmentation and the tensions of the gravitational field. Denudation, which is the degree of erosion intensity, largely depends on the stability of the parent rocks and morpho-climatic zonation [7].

In the territory of Tbilisi, there are up to 60 landslide areas, slopes damaged by gravitational processes with a total length of 21 km, 52 ravines carrying mudflows, and 11 areas of groundwater flooding, both in historical and modern settlements [3]. The development of these processes occurs against the background of modern tectonic movements and erosion processes. Examples of these processes can be seen at Kutsba on the northern slope of Mamadavidi, the Mtatsminda Pantheon, numerous landslide steps of Sololaki Khevi and Tskneti, as well as the end of the Teleti ridge on the right bank of the Mtkvari River and the Mukhadgverdi landslide slopes. Almost 90% of these occurrences are related to improper human economic activity, resulting in the destruction and deformation of several hundred residential buildings, roads, and other infrastructure. For instance, in 1974, two people died in a landslide on the former Agmashenebeli Street due to improper cutting of the Mamadavidi slope [2], and in 2003, four people died on the same street for the same reason.

Landslides that occurred due to incorrectly assessed engineering and geological conditions during the construction process on the Gldani-Khevdzvari section of the Tbilisi access road caused several million GEL in damage to the country's economy. Incorrect design and construction of the access road to the Mukhadgverdi cemetery led to the reactivation of an old landslide slope, creating a direct danger to the cemetery itself. In 1976, during the construction of a tram line on the left side of the Khevdzvari ravine, cutting the foot of the southern slope of Makhati caused the development of a deep landslide, posing a direct danger to 16-story residential buildings. In 1980, a landslide formed on Lebanon Street due to a slope collapse and flooding, posing an immediate threat to a 9-story residential building and a school. The landslide covered the first floor.

Due to incorrect engineering activities, landslide-slump processes occurred on Tskvedadze, Nutsubidze (1984), Kobuleti Sekveli (1986), Petre Bagrationi, Uiaragho, Zedazeni, and Noste (1987) streets. Active landslide deformations were noted on the right slope of the Vere River gorge in 1989, on the territory of Lower Tskneti, and in 1996-97 in the Akhaldaba area of Tskneti and on Gagarin Street. In 2001, several houses collapsed as a result of the landslide of the Lotkin Terrace step and one person died. Since 2003, the slope opposite the circus on Tamar Mepe Avenue has been in active dynamics, where the regressive development trend of the landslide directly threatens the buildings of the Institute of Mathematics. The Vere flood and the development of a mudflow have occurred several times in the past century, and on June 13, 2015, this catastrophic event caused the destruction of buildings and human casualties. A couple of weeks ago, the protective wall of the Mtkvari River bank collapsed near the former restaurant "Mtkva". This was caused by the lateral erosion of the river, washing away the foundation of the wall. All of the above examples speak of a person's careless attitude towards their activities [6].

Since the 2010s, the volume of construction work has increased sharply in both the city center and its surroundings. Due to the format of the article, we will only touch on a few areas where this work is carried out in particularly risky conditions.

From the Sarajishvili metro station to the Mukhiani settlement, along Sheshelidze Street, on a landslide slope, a completely new settlement with two to three-story buildings and yards has emerged. Landslide movements began here back in the 1970s when the construction of the Temk settlement started. Fragmentary gravitational shifts began along the former district and executive committee buildings on the slope covered with deluvium, which were stopped by massive concrete walls. Over time, the walls cracked and slid down, facilitated by actively moving groundwater. Water leaking from the decommissioned sewage network likely exacerbates this issue, as indicated by the presence of water-loving plants along the entire slope. Drinking water and sewage pipes are laid on the same slope, causing water leaks in several places and deepening the trenches where these pipes are located. Structures built under these conditions on such a slope will inevitably be damaged over time.

The cemetery near the fifth microdistrict of Gldani was opened in the early 2000s. In 2010-11, the left slope of the small river flowing into the cemetery began to be developed, which is built of loess-like clays, and the slope is 35-40° degrees. Over time, the concrete frames of the graves overloaded the slope, causing it to lose its gravitational balance and carry the graves towards the riverbed. Some of the graves were so damaged that it was no longer possible to rebury the dead. Only a small number of survivors managed to transfer the remains from the still surviving graves to safe places.

In Vake, on the slope next to the former "Lechkombinati", where landslide bodies were still described by Al. Janelidze [7], there is now a massive construction of capital residential and administrative buildings. Only a small undeveloped area remains, which is likely to be developed soon. The construction foundations under these buildings are unknown, but they are clearly at risk, considering the slope's proximity to the Vere River. Ten years ago, this river flowed into a partially closed collector, yet still caused a tragic flood on June 13, 2015.

There are various interpretations of the causes and consequences of the flood that took place on the Vere River on June 13, 2015. The primary factors contributing to the flood include a significant amount of precipitation - 158 mm falling in the Vere River basin within 4-5 hours, the steep slopes of the valley, deforestation, and the accumulation of eroded rocks in the riverbed due to gravitational processes [4]. Some experts argue that the hydrometeorological stations in the valley had not been operational for an extended period, leading to a lack of data and contributing to the sudden occurrence of the flood [5]. In our view, a combination of natural and human-induced factors played a role, resulting in the transformation of floodwaters into a mudflow. Additionally, poorly constructed tunnels and collectors caused the water to initially stagnate near the Vake-Saburtalo tunnel before flooding the valley from the tunnel to Heroes' Square.

It is important to note that despite this tragic event, the Vere River now flows into a completely closed collector from Tamarashvili Street to Heroes' Square, as construction above it continues to grow. In the event of another flood, which is a possibility, the potential consequences are concerning.

Lochiniskhevi is a suburb of the city where quarrying and processing of inert material occurs in multiple locations. On the left side of the river, shallow landslide bodies have formed in the deluvial layers, which are currently stable. Along the Lilo Bazarba section of the Tbilisi-Kakheti highway, slopes have been cut in various areas and the land in front of the slope has been

leveled, likely for future development. These almost vertical cuts in the slopes, if not reinforced, will eventually erode and collapse due to gravitational processes such as landslides and landslide steps.

Conclusions

Due to its complex natural conditions, Tbilisi is under strong anthropogenic influence, and its geoecological state is under increased threat. This is a result of the large-scale construction works underway in the city and its surroundings in recent years, which are accompanied by geoecological complications. A positive solution to this problem is only possible with a comprehensive assessment of the basic state of the city's natural environment. This assessment can be carried out as a result of coordinated, complex research work by various scientific and practical organizations working on this issue. Documentation should be created to reflect the current real situation, including maps showing the spread of geological, geomorphological, and exodynamic processes, as well as a scheme for conducting construction and economic works that is recommended for the actual situation of each district. This will help minimize damage and losses caused by human impact, and is necessary for the continued safe development of the city and the development of an optimal scheme for the use of the city's territory. Such work should be carried out continuously to update data and make necessary corrections.

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